

Entrustment and Teachers' Participation in School-Initiated Activities With Contextual Performance As Moderator

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Abstract. The current study was set to evaluate whether contextual performance significantly moderates the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities. In this study, the researcher selected 195 public secondary school teachers from Cluster 5, Davao City, as the respondents. The stratified random sampling technique was employed to select the respondents. A non-experimental, quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational method was used. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Hierarchical Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that entrustment, teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance were rated as moderately extensive. Furthermore, correlation analysis revealed a significant relationship between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, moderated by contextual performance. Hierarchical regression analysis proved that contextual performance significantly moderates the interaction between teachers' pedagogical strategies and self-directedness among learners. In other words, parental support is a significant moderator of the relationship between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5, Davao City.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management 2. entrustment 3. participation in school-initiated activities 4. contextual performance 5. Davao City

Date Received: May 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: June 15, 2025 — Date Published: July 12, 2025

1. Introduction

Schools help learners acquire skills in socialization, communication, and the development of their academic ability. Similarly, schools serve as venues where parents and other stakeholders can participate in the teaching and learning processes, as well as other educational reforms implemented by the Department of Education (DepEd). However, the development of quality education is not the sole responsibility of schools. Hand-in-hand with the school are people who complement and supplement each other in achieving the desired educational goals for the learners. Hence, school personnel and other school partners must be attentive to the learners' welfare and performance in school. They have the responsibility to be involved and be sensitive to the learners' problems and development in school. With their aid in the learners' education, positive cooperation and communication between the school and them will foster the learners' progress, and better academic performance will be attained. Indeed, research findings demonstrate that through the implementation of school-initiated programs,

school stakeholders have been empowered in decision-making, resulting in high levels of parental and community participation (Gamage, 2016). Some scholars argue that parental and community participation in schools has led to more effective schools and improved student achievement (Werf et al., 2014). In the Asian context, for instance, Smith (2016) found that parental involvements are significantly related to all kinds of student achievements. They clarify that parental involvement has been the most effective intervention in improving the overall quality of education, and the amount of voluntary work done by parents has a positive impact on students' academic achievement. Furthermore, Pepito and Acibar (2019) asserted that there are schools that stakeholders scarcely visit due to a lack of understanding. Accordingly, when stakeholders are involved, they do not prioritize the schools because they do not understand their roles and responsibilities in becoming partners of the school. Similarly, Vicera and Bentero (2013) agreed that some school administrators are apprehensive about involving teachers and other stakeholders, fearing that they may seize control of the institution and obstruct the decision-making of school heads. They appear to assume control over the schools. Principals and school administrators often relax their standards because they appreciate their stakeholders' disagreement with the school organization. Previous investigations have found that stakeholders' interest in participating in school-based management can empower schools to develop a better quality educational process and improve student outcomes (Lindberg Vanyushyn, 2013). As noted by Khattri et al. (2012), stakeholder involvement in school-initiated activities has been the most effective intervention in improving the quality of education and has a positive effect on students' academic achievement. Additionally, Moradi et al. (2012) noted that participation in school-based management may also improve teachers' morale, as they feel empowered and trusted by their superiors. Additionally, previous studies have indicated a relationship between teachers' trust in their students and their participation in school-initiated activities. For instance, Almutairi (2020) found that when teachers are empowered, show a positive attitude towards work, and allow creativity and innovation, they are more likely to copy or imitate their leaders. In addition, the study conducted by Ambali et al. (2011) found that the strong component of management, such as crew involvement, is positively correlated with employee ethical behavior and employee involvement in organizational activities. Consensus decision-making enables a leader to view their rank or leadership position within the organization as merely a set of responsibilities, rather than a defining characteristic of their identity. Jacobs (2014) defines organizational entrustment as the individual's ability to get someone to do something they want them to do. In this sense, Hobbs and Moreland (2009) made it clear that empowerment enables an individual to acquire skills to engage in their work, assign control, and influence settings that affect their lives. Furthermore, Moran (2015) highlighted that when teachers perceive themselves as being entrusted and included in the decision-making process, they are more likely to act to change and impact education in classrooms and schools by pursuing professional growth and developing ownership of their classroom and school. Most investigations into teachers' participation in school-initiated activities have focused on elementary school teachers, and the majority of these studies have employed qualitative approaches. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to address the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, specifically in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher employed a descriptive-correlational design utilizing multiple regression analysis to gain a better understanding of

teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, as determined by entrustment, which is found to be scarce. This study may provide additional insights into the existing literature on the influence of teacher entrustment on teachers' participation in school-initiated activities.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— This section reviews studies on teacher entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance, highlighting their indicators and significance.

*1.1.1. Entrustment—*Entrustment refers to granting teachers the authority, confidence, and responsibility to influence decisions and improve teaching practices (Jacobs, 2014; Merriam-Webster, 2012). It enhances teacher morale, performance, and ownership, contributing to school effectiveness (Wall, 2012; Sagnak, 2012). Empowered teachers engage in decision-making, fostering collaboration and shared leadership (Devos, Tuytens, Hulpia, 2014; Kirika, 2011). Studies show that entrustment evolves through phases: initiation (1–3 years), growth (4–8 years), and maintenance (9+ years), with self-efficacy plateauing in later years (Hobbs Moreland, 2009). Mutual respect and teacher empowerment improve school culture and professional growth (Tse Mitchel, 2010; Moran, 2015). Conversely, disempowerment from rigid curricula and inadequate support reduces teacher motivation and creativity (Overton, 2009; Rinkevich, 2011).

Entrustment is linked to professional relationships, intrinsic motivation, and job satisfaction (Kaur, 2013; Crawford, 2010; Amouli Youran, 2014). Self-determination, autonomy, and professional collaboration are crucial components (Van den Broeck et al., 2010; Watson, 2014). Teachers with autonomy in curriculum and instruction demonstrate greater commitment and effectiveness (Stacy, 2013; Mullick, 2014). Indicators of Entrustment: Work Values: A sense of purpose and professionalism (Feinauer, 2017; Lee Nie, 2014). Work Proficiency:

Confidence and competence in teaching roles (Bogler Nir, 2012; Jackson Marriott, 2012). Self-Determination: The freedom to initiate and sustain tasks (Van den Broeck et al., 2010). Autonomy: Influence over outcomes and decision-making (Stacy, 2013).

*1.1.2. Participation in School-Initiated Activities—*School-based management (SBM) decentralizes decision-making, giving schools autonomy to meet local needs (Abdulla Al Kaabi, 2015; Oswald, 2014). It empowers teachers and principals, promotes shared leadership, and enhances accountability (Khattri et al., 2010; Lindgerg Vanyushyn, 2013). SBM encourages community participation, improving teacher morale and student outcomes (Vernez, Karam, Marshall, 2012; Moradi, Bin Hussin, Barzegar, 2012).

Challenges include lack of readiness and the need for proper training and capacity-building among school councils and stakeholders (Pañares Palmes, 2014). Building school-community partnerships also supports resource allocation and student success (Cabardo, 2016).

Indicators of Participation:

Leadership and Governance: Effective instructional and administrative leadership (Döş Savaş, 2015; Murphy et al., 2013).

Curriculum and Instruction: Teacher involvement in curriculum decisions (Ismail, 2012; Awang, Ahmad, Zin, 2010).

Accountability and Continuous Improvement: Sustaining quality teaching practices and engagement (Roorda et al., 2011; Shukla, 2014).

Resource Management: Efficient allocation of materials and technology to support teaching (Ye, 2016; Wanjala Wanjala, 2017).

*1.1.3. Contextual Performance—*Contextual performance involves behaviors that support the social and organizational environment of teaching (Koopmans et al., 2014). It is influenced by working conditions, collaboration, and administrative support (Buchanan, 2010;

Boyd et al., 2011). Positive teacher relationships and professional engagement foster motivation, efficiency, and job satisfaction (Rossi, 2018; Christian et al., 2011).

Teachers with strong work ethics and emotional resilience demonstrate better performance and lower burnout (Herlambang, 2013; Karatas Gules, 2010). A collaborative and supportive environment spreads positive energy, enhancing both individual and team performance (Nick, 2012; Hakanen Roodt, 2010).

1.2. Synthesis—Teacher involvement, encompassing both entrustment and participation in school-initiated activities, is crucial for a positive and effective learning environment. These elements foster a supportive atmosphere, encourage teacher development, and ultimately contribute to improved student outcomes. Teacher entrustment is a crucial technique that fosters autonomy, accountability, professional development, and increased job satisfaction. It entails delegating responsibilities, such as facilitating study groups or implementing innovative teaching methodologies, to cultivate a sense of ownership and accountability. Delegation also enables educators to enhance their competencies and broaden their knowledge. Teachers' participation in school-initiated activities can enhance learning settings, as they possess significant insights into learning styles and student needs. They contribute to curriculum development by engaging in professional learning communities, where they interact, exchange best practices, and offer feedback. Engagement in school enhancement initiatives, such as action research and mentorship, can lead to beneficial transformations within the school environment. Furthermore, active participation in school activities can foster a more stimulating and supportive educational environment for students, thereby enhancing both their academic and personal development. Consequently, empowering educators through delegation and active involvement in school activities

is crucial for establishing a dynamic learning environment. Moreover, Teacher entrustment (the extent to which teachers feel empowered and trusted with autonomy in their roles) and participation in school-initiated activities are indeed associated with contextual performance, which encompasses behaviors that go beyond formal job requirements and contribute to the broader functioning and success of the school environment. Research suggests that when teachers are entrusted with and actively involved in school initiatives, it can positively influence their motivation, confidence, and engagement, ultimately impacting their overall effectiveness and, in turn, the school's effectiveness. Entrustment and participation in school-initiated activities can significantly impact contextual performance. Entrustment enhances teachers' sense of ownership, motivation, and job satisfaction, leading to greater commitment to the school's mission and goals. It also fosters innovation and leadership, encouraging them to take on new roles and contribute to school improvement initiatives. Collaboration with colleagues and stakeholders strengthens the school's organizational culture, improving communication and fostering a supportive learning environment. On-the-job professional development provides opportunities for teachers to gain new skills and perspectives, improving their teaching practices and contextual performance. These teacher-level impacts can translate to positive outcomes for students, as a more engaged and empowered teaching staff creates a more effective and supportive learning environment. Factors influencing these associations include organizational support, school culture, and individual teacher factors. Teachers who receive adequate support and resources are more likely to be successful and experience positive outcomes.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—The study was anchored on Systems Theory by Von Bertalanffy (1968) which reacts against reductionism and attempts to revive the unity of

science, emphasizes that a phenomenon, an entity, or an organization is comprised with real systems and that these real systems are open to, and interact with, their environments, and that they can acquire qualitatively new properties through emergence, resulting in continual evolution. Rather than reducing an entity of the school to the properties of its parts or elements, such as administrators, teachers, and stakeholders, systems theory focuses on the arrangement of and relations between the parts, which connect them into a whole. It was a transdisciplinary approach that counters reductionism by emphasizing the interconnectedness

Lastly, O'Donnell (2018) notes that teachers' entrustment improves the relationship among professionals. Teachers' perceptions of a supportive working condition were positively related to their belief and capability to perform the teaching job for inclusion, in turn influencing their ratings of the severity of and their confidence in managing commonly experienced challenging behaviors in inclusive classrooms. Likewise, Hosford and O'Sullivan (2016) viewed that positive teaching impacted their willingness to ask for assistance and seek help through administrator-to-teacher or teacher-to-teacher supports. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable is the teacher entrustment or the individual's ability to get someone to do something they want them to do. As proposed by Jacobs (2014) the measures of teacher entrustment are work values or the importance of a work goal or purpose that is judged about an individual's own beliefs or expectations; work proficiency or the individual's belief and capability to perform fixed tasks with skill; self-determination or the an individual's perception of choice in initiating and sustaining their action with tasks; and autonomy or the degree to which an individual can influence outcomes in the workplace. The dependent variable of the study is teach-

and interactions within a whole system rather than focusing on its parts. It argues that understanding the relationships between components is crucial for comprehending the system's behavior and properties. In addition, Crawford (2010) proposed that employee entrustment is linked to organizational collaboration in terms of service quality. Accordingly, entrustment can be utilized as a means of creating service quality, thereby creating a competitive advantage. Entrustment empowers employees to take responsibility for the service encounter, thereby creating an environment where employees are emotionally invested.

ers' participation in school-initiated activities or the approach or strategy by which authority is delegated from central administration to individual schools. Accordingly, the measures of teachers' participation in school-initiated activities include leadership and governance, or the ability to lead in a fair and just manner; curriculum and instruction, or the ability to implement instructional curricula; and accountability and continuous improvement, or the ability to maintain ongoing improvement processes in the school. Teachers who are engaged in their work can also be decisive in transforming their schools into successful and efficient institutions, as well as in managing and allocating resources efficiently. Lastly, the mediating variable is contextual performance or the individual behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine the significance of the moderating effect of contextual performance on the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5, Davao City. Specifically, the study intended to attain the following objectives:

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

- (1) What is the extent of entrustment of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) work proficiency;
 - (2) impact;
 - (3) work values; and
 - (4) self-determination?
- (2) What is the extent of teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in terms of:
 - (1) leadership and governance;
 - (2) curriculum and instruction;
 - (3) accountability and continuous improvement; and
 - (4) resources management?
- (3) What is the extent of teachers' contextual performance as moderator?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship among entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance of teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City?
- (5) Do contextual performance have a significant moderating effect on the interaction between entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities of teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City?

1.5. *Hypotheses*—The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship among entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance of teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City. H02: Contextual performance does not have a significant moderating effect on the interaction between entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities of teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City.

2. Methodology

This study employed a descriptive design with purposively selected respondents to ensure the collection of relevant insights. Data were collected through a validated questionnaire and then analyzed using descriptive statistics and thematic methods to identify patterns and themes, thereby providing a clear understanding of the research focus.

2.1. *Research Design*—The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research, which is designed to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic, and an objective stance. It focuses on numeric and unchanging data and detailed, convergent reasoning, generating a variety of ideas about a research problem (Babbie et al., 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013), a correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes a cause-and-effect relationship between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables simultaneously and helped describe the relationship between the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also examined the relationship among three variables – entrustment, participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance of teachers. The study aims to investigate whether contextual performance moderates the interaction between entrustment and participation in school-initiated activities among teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents in the study were secondary school teachers from Cluster 5 schools in Davao City. In this study, the 195 respondents were selected

through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata (Salkind, 2020). Furthermore, the five schools served as the basis for the stratification. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were used to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City, who were not subject to any administrative complaints and had voluntarily signed the ICF, were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed researcher-designed questionnaires tailored to the current investigation. The questionnaire is composed of two parts. The first part focused on the entrustment indicated by work proficiency, impact, work values, and self-determination. The Cronbach coefficient value for this instrument is 0.982, described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. More so, this questionnaire was subjected to content validity by a panel of experts to test its validity and reliability. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all items in each dimension under their respective domains. In responding to the questionnaire, the respondents used a 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of entrustment, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The entrustment of teachers is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The entrustment of teachers is often-times observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The entrustment of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The entrustment of teachers is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The entrustment of teachers is never observed.

The second part focused on stakeholders' participation in school-initiated activities. The questionnaire is composed of items indicated with leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management and resources. The reliability of the new scale was assessed using a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.930, inter-

preted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. More so, this questionnaire was subjected to content validity by a panel of experts to test its validity. As a guide in determining the extent of stakeholders' participation in school-initiated activities, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities is never manifested.

The third part of the instrument concerns the contextual performance of teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City. The Cronbach coefficient value for this instrument is 0.87, indicating high reliability and consistency. In response to the questionnaire, the items were modified to suit the context of this study and were answered using a 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the teachers' contextual performance, the researcher employed the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' contextual performance is always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' contextual performance is oftentimes evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' contextual performance is sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' contextual performance is seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' contextual performance is never evident.

2.4. Design and Procedure—The researcher took steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School, which was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed by the school's division superintendent and the school principals of the selected secondary public schools in Cluster 5, Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after obtaining approval to conduct the study. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the study respondents were given sufficient testing time to complete the questionnaires. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After retrieving the data from the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data by indicator. Afterward, each

score was subjected to both descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines for carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires, along with supporting authors, were submitted for further evaluation. After approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. This study adhered to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher ensured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who would be the real source of information, to protect their identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, access was limited to the researcher alone.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results derived from the data collected. It is organized according to the objectives outlined in Chapter 1. The findings detail the levels of entrustment, teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual performance within Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City. Furthermore, it explores the significant relationship between entrustment and teachers' participation in these activities, moderated by contextual performance. Additionally, the chapter examines the moderating effect of contextual performance on the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City.

3.1. *Entrustment of Teachers in Cluster 5 Secondary Schools in Davao City*—

3.1.1. Work Values—Specifically, examining the domain of meaning, results in Table 1 reveal that its category mean is 3.82, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain of entrustment to secondary school teachers is often observed. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.38 to 4.10. It is noteworthy that the item 'Find-

2.6. Data Analysis—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teacher entrustment, teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, and contextual factors. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Partial Correlation Analysis. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (entrustment) and dependent (teachers' participation in school-initiated activities) variables, with a moderator (contextual performance) variable. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 4. Hierarchical Regression Analysis was applied to evaluate the moderating effect of contextual performance on the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities. This analysis was used to provide the answer to objective 5.

ing my tasks in school personally meaningful' has a mean rating of 3.38, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as an item that is sometimes observed. The item Believing that the work I do at school is important to me has a mean rating of 4.10, described as extensive and interpreted as an item that was often observed. The extensive rating on teacher empowerment in terms of meaning implies that the respondents' believed teaching has great value in so-

ciety as well as in their own lives. This finding supports Feinauer’s (2017) idea that teachers’ autonomy and administrative support increase, as does their empowerment and professional-

ism. A sense of professionalism is closely tied to feeling a sense of purpose in their work, such as identity or what is referred to as meaning.

Table 1. Extent of Entrustment in Terms of Work Values

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Perceiving that my task as an elementary public-school teacher is meaningful to me.	3.99	Extensive
2. Believing that the work I do at school is important to me.	4.10	Extensive
3. Finding my tasks in school personally meaningful.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.82	Extensive

3.1.2. *Work Proficiency*—The results in Table 2 indicate that entrustment in terms of work proficiency was assessed by secondary school teachers as extensive, with a category mean of 3.53, which is interpreted as often observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.38 to 3.78. On the other hand, the item ‘Having mastered the skills necessary for my teaching job at the school’ has a mean rating of 3.38, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item that the respondents sometimes observe. On the other hand, the item, being confident about my ability to do my job at school, reflects a mean of 3.77, described as ex-

tensive, which was interpreted as an item that is often observed by teachers. This finding means that teachers often believed in their capability to perform fixed tasks with skill. This result supports the finding of Jackson and Marriott (2012) that creating opportunities for teachers to become more involved with new initiatives and responsibilities develops their autonomy. Empowering teachers requires principals to elicit changes in their role, which are likely to be primarily evident in the level of authority that individuals have on the job. Empowerment encourages team members to learn about themselves and others, enabling them to relate and interact more effectively.

Table 2. Extent of Entrustment in Terms of Work Proficiency

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Being confident about my ability to do my job at school.	3.78	Extensive
2. Being self-assured about my capabilities to perform my work activities at school.	3.42	Extensive
3. Having mastered the skills necessary for my teaching job at the school.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.53	Extensive

3.1.3. *Self-Determination*—In terms of self-determination, Table 3 shows an extensive category mean rating of 3.56, indicating that this domain of entrustment is often observed

by secondary school teachers. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.24 to 3.83. The item, having considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I perform my

teaching job at the school, reflects a mean rating of 3.24, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, which has significant autonomy in how I perform my tasks at school, shows a rating of 3.83, described as extensive, and was oftentimes observed among teachers. This suggests that teachers' perception of choice in

initiating and sustaining their action with tasks is often observed among the respondents. This finding supports the idea of Van den Broeck et al. (2010) that determination paves the way for an individual to determine his capability to execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations.

Table 3. Extent of Entrustment in Terms of Self-Determination

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Having significant autonomy in how I do my tasks at the school.	3.83	Extensive
2. Deciding on my own how to go about doing my work at the school.	3.37	Extensive
3. Having considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I do my teaching job at the school.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.48	Extensive

3.1.4. *Autonomy*—In terms of impact, Table 4 shows a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.38, indicating that this domain of teacher entrustment was sometimes observed by secondary school teachers. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.02 to 3.52. The item, Having significant influence

over what happens in my school, reflects a mean rating of 3.02, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, having a great deal of control over what happens in my school shows a rating of 3.52, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among teachers.

Table 4. Extent of Entrustment in Terms of Autonomy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Perceiving that impact at the school is large.	3.46	Extensive
2. Having a great deal of control over what happens in my school.	3.52	Extensive
3. Having significant influence over what happens in my school.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.33	Moderately Extensive

The moderately extensive rating on this domain suggests that the ability to influence outcomes in the workplace is sometimes observed among the teachers. This finding supports Stacy's (2013) idea that empowered teachers are professionals who possess the authority to create curricula, administer lessons, and ef-

fectively teach their students. Lastly, Table 5 presents a summary of the extent of entrustment of teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, entrustment obtained an overall mean score of 3, which is considered consistent and is often observed by secondary school teachers. Adding more, the re-

sults on the table show that entrustment in terms of work values acquired the highest mean score of 3.82, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while entrustment in terms of autonomy got the lowest mean score of 3.33, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the secondary school teachers.

Table 5. Summary Table on the Extent of Entrustment on Teachers in Cluster 5 Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Work Values	3.82	Extensive
Work Proficiency	3.53	Extensive
Self-Determination	3.48	Extensive
Autonomy	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.54	Extensive

The result of the analysis implies that the secondary school teachers often show the ability to get someone to do something they want them to do. This finding supports the view of Devos et al. (2014) that entrustment is a dynamic, interactive influence process comprised of the concerted action of people working together, which brings about a situation in which the amount of energy created is greater than the sum of the individual actions. Accordingly, a school that follows a leadership framework of elevating teacher-leaders was one that adopts a model empowering groups of teachers to act as a professional practice within their school.

Meanwhile, the item Encouraging the team to regularly review the school plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges, and opportunities shows a rating of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as an item that was oftentimes manifested among the teachers. This suggests that the extent to which the school's heads led in a fair and just manner was often reflected in the actions of the teachers. This finding supports the view of Döş and Savaş (2015) that the lenses of leadership contribute to the success of school heads in performing a lengthy list of responsibilities related

3.2. *Teachers' Participation in School-Initiated Activities—*

3.2.1. *Leadership and Governance—*In terms of leadership and governance, Table 6 shows an extensive category mean rating of 3.68, indicating that this domain of stakeholders' participation in school-initiated activities is often led by teachers. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.66 to 3.71. The item contributes to addressing the training and development needs of the school and the community, with a mean rating of 3.66, described as extensive and interpreted as an item that is often observed.

to school leadership. Accordingly, the task of the school head as manager of the school is no longer enough, today's principals are accountable for the oversight of teaching, curriculum, and assessment cycles, evaluation of teachers, fostering relationships with teachers and other stakeholders, evaluating and implementing discipline plans, developing a multi-year plan for needed resources, all while still managing the school building.

3.2.2. *Curriculum and Instruction—*The results in Table 7 indicate that the domain, curriculum, and instruction were assessed by sec-

Table 6. Extent of Teachers’ Participation in School-Initiated Activities in Terms of Leadership and Governance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Contributing to the effort to develop the school plans.	3.67	Extensive
2. Encouraging the team to regularly review the school plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges, and opportunities.	3.71	Extensive
3. Perceiving that the school and community collaboratively defines the organizational structure and responsibilities of stakeholders.	3.69	Extensive
4. Thinking that a network has been collaboratively established and is continuously improved by the school community.	3.69	Extensive
5. Contributing to the effort in addressing the training and development needs of the school and the community.	3.66	Extensive
Mean	3.68	Extensive

ondary school teachers as extensive, with a category mean of 3.69, which is interpreted as often manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.38 to 4.02. On the one hand, the item, Which Encourages the administration and other external stakeholders to ensure that learners develop their creative thinking and problem-solving skills, has a mean rating of 3.38, described as moderately extensive and in-

terpreted as indicating that the item sometimes manifests. On the other hand, the item, Taking responsibility in ensuring that the learning systems were regularly and collaboratively monitored to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community, reflects a mean of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested.

This finding supports Ismail’s (2012) proposition that curriculum and instruction are the most important aspects of educational institutions, as they are the primary purpose of school establishment. Curriculum management, as described by Ismail (2012), was influenced by factors such as the magnitude/number of investments of time, energy, and money individuals contribute to an organization, as well as a perceived lack of alternatives. The author pointed out that even if an employee may dislike working at an organization, costs such as pay level and incentives such as yearly bonuses would retain an employee since they may not be able to achieve the same level of accrued monetary capital elsewhere.

3.2.3. *Management of Resources*—Specifically, examining the domain of management

of resources, the results in Table 8 reveal that the category mean is 3.68, described as extensive, indicating that this particular domain of teachers’ participation in school-initiated activities is oftentimes observed. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.61 to 3.71. It is noteworthy that the item ‘Engaging in regular dialogues for planning and resource programming, and supporting the implementation of community education plans’ has a mean rating of 3.61, described as extensive and interpreted as the item is often manifested. In contrast, the item Participating in resource inventory which serves as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization has a mean rating of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the secondary school teachers. The result

Table 7. Extent of Teachers’ Participation in School-Initiated Activities in Terms of Curriculum and Instruction

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Being involved in ensuring that the curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	3.73	Extensive
2. Helping the school in ensuring that programs are fully implemented and closely monitored to address performance discrepancies, benchmark best practices, coach low performers, mentor potential leaders, reward high achievement, and maintain an environment that makes learning meaningful and enjoyable.	3.92	Extensive
3. Encouraging the administration and other external stakeholders to ensure that the creative thinking and problem-solving skills of the learners are developed.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
4. Taking responsibility in ensuring that the learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.	4.02	Extensive
5. Taking part in ensuring that appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved, and assessment results are contextualized to the learners and local situation in the attainment of relevant life skills.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.69	Extensive

implies that the teacher’s availability and responsiveness to the students’ needs are sometimes manifested. This finding supports the view of Zadjia and Gamage (2010) that establishing school-community partnerships is anchored on extensive and sound research which had supported the need for. The establishment of mean-

ingful partnerships with education stakeholders not only allows non-educators to share the responsibility of educational delivery but also makes education more relevant and responsive to the needs of the students, in particular, and the wider community, in general.

3.2.4. *Accountability and Continuous Improvement*—The results in Table 9 shows that the domain of accountability and continuous improvement was assessed by secondary school teachers as extensive, with a category mean of 3.67, interpreted as oftentimes observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.38 to 3.95. On the one hand, the item, ‘Taking part in developing and deciding on the accountability assessment criteria tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes,’ has a mean rating of 3.38, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as indicating that the item

sometimes manifested. On the other hand, the item ‘Helping in defining and setting roles as well as responsibilities of accountable person (s) and collective body (ies)’ reflects a mean of 3.95, described as extensive, interpreted as often manifested. This finding supports the view of Balakrishnan et al. (2013) that increasing the engagement level of stakeholders improved their willingness to remain in the service for a long time. The willingness of an individual to remain in the same job can be improved by addressing non-financial drivers of engagement, such as communication, recognition, manager/supervisor support (relationship), work engagement, teamwork, and role clarity.

Table 8. Extent of Teachers’ Participation in School-Initiated Activities in Terms of Management of Resources

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Participating in resource inventory which serves as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.71	Extensive
2. Engaging in regular dialogues for planning and resource programming, and supporting the implementation of community education plans.	3.61	Extensive
3. Helping ensure that there is a community-developed resource management system towards judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	3.70	Extensive
4. Participating in the monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management.	3.68	Extensive
5. Helping to manage and sustain an established system of partnership with external stakeholders.	3.68	Extensive
Mean	3.68	Extensive

Table 9. Extent of Teachers’ Participation in School-Initiated Activities in Terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Helping in defining and setting roles as well as responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies.	3.95	Extensive
2. Recognizing achievement of goals based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system can help address gaps through appropriate action.	3.90	Extensive
3. Helping in the enhancement of the accountability system to ensure that the management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	3.71	Extensive
4. Taking part in developing and deciding on the accountability assessment criteria tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5. Participating in the school-initiated periodic assessment and shared feedback.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.67	Extensive

Lastly, Table 10 shows the summary of the extent of teachers’ participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, the school-based management participation of teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.68, which is descriptively rated as extensive and interpreted as often manifested. Additionally, the table indicates that stakeholders’ participa-

tion in school-initiated activities, in terms of curriculum and instruction, acquired the highest mean score of 3.69, described as extensive and interpreted as often manifested. In contrast, stakeholders’ participation in school-initiated activities in terms of accountability and continuous improvement acquired the lowest mean score of 3.67, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by teachers.

Table 10. Summary Table on the Extent of Teachers’ Participation in School-Initiated Activities

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Leadership and Governance	3.68	Extensive
Curriculum and Instruction	3.69	Extensive
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.67	Extensive
Management of Resources	3.68	Extensive
Overall	3.68	Extensive

The result denotes that teachers oftentimes manifested that school management tasks are set according to the characteristics and needs of the school itself, and therefore school members including supervisors, principal, teachers, parents and students have a much greater autonomy and responsibility for the use of resources to carry out effective education activities and solve problems. This finding is congruent to the view of Barrera-Osorio et al. (2010) that most school-based management programs try to empower principals and teachers, and strengthen their professional motivation, thereby enhancing their sense of ownership of the school. The principal’s role as the primary decision maker is dramatically changed under school-based management to involve combination of principals, teachers, parents, and other school members in responsibility and decision-making. Therefore,

school-based management flourishes leadership skills by allowing competent individuals in the schools to make decisions that will improve learning.

3.3. *Contextual Performance of Teachers—*

The results in Table 11 show that contextual performance was assessed by the secondary school teachers as extensive, with a category mean of 3.44, interpreted as oftentimes evident. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.22 to 3.95. On the one hand, the item ‘Starting new tasks myself, when my old ones were finished’ has a mean rating of 3.22, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item that is sometimes evident. On the other hand, the item Taking extra responsibilities reflects a mean of 3.95, described as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes evident.

Table 11. Extent of Contextual Performance of Teachers

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Taking extra responsibilities.	3.95	Extensive
2. Starting new tasks myself when my old ones were finished.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
3. Taking on challenging work tasks, when available.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
4. Working on keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5. Working on keeping my job skills up-to-date.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
6. Coming up with creative solutions to new problems.	3.45	Extensive
7. Keep looking for new challenges in my job.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.44	Extensive

This means that the individual behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function are oftentimes evident. This finding supports the view of Boyd et al. (2011) that such working conditions, including behavioral climate and administrative support, were found to harm teacher turnover rates, especially among novice educators working in schools with low-income and low-achieving students. Furthermore, the result aligns with Hodges' (2015) idea that when individuals become accustomed to behaviors that support organizational success, it will indirectly enhance their working performance.

3.4. Relationship Between Entrustment and Teachers' Participation In School-Initiated Activities with Contextual Performance as Moderator—The results on the analysis on the relationship between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance are presented. Partial Correlation Analysis was utilized. Table 12 shows the relationships between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance. It shows that entrustment has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .964, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of

the entrustment changes, the extent of teachers' participation in school-initiated activities also significantly changes when moderated by contextual performance. Moreover, the table also shows that the entrustment in terms of work values, work proficiency, self-determination, and autonomy obtained are significantly correlated with teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance with p-values of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .756, p < 0.05$), ($r = .823, p < 0.05$), ($r = .992, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .547, p < 0.05$), respectively. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance. This supports Donnell's (2018) view that teacher entrustment improves coordination and participation among professionals. Accordingly, teachers' perceptions of a supportive working condition related positively to their belief and capability to perform the teaching job for inclusion, in turn influencing their ratings of the severity of and their confidence in managing commonly experienced challenging behaviors in inclusive classrooms. Likewise, the result aligns with the idea of Hosford and O'Sullivan (2016) that entrustment influences one's willingness to ask for assistance and seek help through administrator-to-teacher or teacher-to-teacher supports.

Table 12. Relationship Between Teacher Entrustment and Stakeholders' Participation in School-Initiated Activities in Cluster 1 Secondary Schools in Davao City

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Work Values	0.756*	0.000	Reject H0
Work Proficiency	0.823*	0.000	Reject H0
Self-Determination	0.992*	0.000	Reject H0
Autonomy	0.547*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Entrustment	0.964*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

3.5. *Moderating Effect of Contextual Performance on the Interaction Between Entrustment and Teachers' Participation in School-Initiated Activities*—The moderating effect of contextual performance (CP) on the interaction between entrustment (En) and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) was tested using hierarchical regression analysis. Results in Table 12 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of entrustment (En) and

teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) were = 0.105, S.E. = 0.056, $p < 0.05$. Contextual performance (CP) and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) were =0.211, S.E.=0.049, $p < 0.05$. When entrustment (En) and contextual performance (CP) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 63.8 % of the variance in teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) ($R^2 = 0.638$, $p < .05$).

Table 13. Moderating Effect of Contextual Performance on the Interaction Between Entrustment and Teachers' Participation in School-Initiated Activities

Step	Variable	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Step 1	Entrustment (En)	.105	.131	.056	.000	Reject H_0
	Contextual Performance (CP)	.211	.078	.049	.000	Reject H_0
	$R^2 = 0.638$		F-value = 117.884**		p-value = 0.000	
Step 2	Entrustment (En)	.384**	.576	.031	.000	Reject H_0
	Contextual Performance (CP)	.177**	.126	.048	.000	Reject H_0
	Moderator (En × CP)	.224**	.089	.052	.000	Reject H_0
	$R^2 = 0.742$		F-value = 132.087**		p-value = 0.000	

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$.** The results show that both entrustment and contextual performance significantly influence teachers' participation in school-initiated activities. The interaction between entrustment and contextual performance further strengthens the model in Step 2.

Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of entrustment (En) and self-directedness (SD) among learners were = 0.384, S.E. = .031, $p < 0.05$; contextual performance (CP) and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) were =0.177, S.E. = 0.048, $p < 0.05$; and moderator (En*CP) and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) were =0.224, S.E.= 0.052, $p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between entrustment (En) and contextual performance (CP) was added, the percentage of variance in teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) was 74.20 % ($R^2 = 0.742$; $p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression

equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 10.40 % of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.104$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as contextual performance (CP) had significantly moderated the interaction between entrustment (En) and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP). This is in consonance with Crawford's (2010) study, which suggests that entrustment can be utilized as a means of creating service quality, thereby creating a competitive advantage. Entrustment empowers employees to take responsibility for the service encounter, thereby creating an environment where employees are emotionally invested. Likewise, this

finding aligns with Boey's (2010) observation that teacher inclusion in planning contributes to higher job satisfaction, motivation, commitment, improved communication, and more efficient decision-making among teachers. Lastly, the finding supports Tuckman's (1968) model of work participation, which explains how a team's maturity and ability to develop relationships change as leadership style evolves. The model recognizes that groups do not start off being fully formed and functioning. It suggests that teams grow through clearly defined stages, from their creation as groups of individuals to cohesive, task-focused teams.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section outlines the key conclusions and proposed recommendations derived from the study. The analysis is grounded in the scholarly works cited in the earlier chapters, and the findings are directly aligned with the research questions and objectives initially established in the study. The study aimed to examine how contextual performance influences the relationship between entrustment and teachers' involvement in activities initiated by their schools. To accomplish this, a non-experimental quantitative approach was employed, specifically using a descriptive-predictive method. A total of 195 secondary public school teachers from Cluster 5 in Davao City were selected as participants through a stratified random sampling method. Data collection utilized refined and enhanced survey instruments, adapted from existing tools. Prior to full deployment, the instrument was pilot tested in a nearby school to validate its reliability and ensure strong internal consistency among the items.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: The extent of entrustment of teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.54, with a descriptive rating of 'extensive'. Additionally, entrustment in terms of work values, work proficiency, self-determination, and autonomy yielded mean scores of 3.82, 3.53, 3.48, and 3.33, respectively. The extent of teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.68, with a descriptive rating of 'extensive'. Additionally, teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability, continuous improvement, and resource management, yielded mean scores of 3.68, 3.69, 3.67, and 3.68, respectively. Moreover, the contextual performance of teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City yielded a mean score of 3.44, which is described as extensive. The results showed that entrustment has a significant positive relationship with teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.964$, $p < 0.05$). In addition, findings reflected that contextual performance is a significant moderator on the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City. The analysis showed that when an interaction between entrustment (En) and contextual performance (CP) was added, the percentage of variance in teachers' participation in school-initiated activities (TP) was 74.20 % ($R^2 = 0.742$; $p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an

additional 10.40 % of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.104$).

4.2. Conclusion—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Entrustment of teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City was rated as extensive. Additionally, trust in terms of work values, work proficiency, and self-determination was rated as extensive, while teacher empowerment in terms of autonomy was rated as moderately extensive. The result suggests that secondary school teachers often possess the ability to persuade others to do something they want them to do. The teachers' participation in school-initiated activities was described as extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' participation in school-initiated activities, encompassing leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management, is rated as extensive. It denotes that teachers oftentimes manifest that school-initiated activity tasks are set according to the characteristics and needs of the school itself. Therefore, school members, including supervisors, principals, teachers, parents, and students, have a much greater autonomy and responsibility for the use of resources to carry out practical education activities and solve problems. The contextual performance of teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City was extensive. This means that the individual behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function are often evident. The result showed entrustment has a significant positive relationship with teachers' participation in school-initiated activities when moderated by contextual performance. This means that as the extent of the teacher entrustment changes, stakeholders' participation in school-initiated activities also significantly changes when moderated by

contextual performance. Lastly, contextual performance had a significant moderating effect on the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities. This study emphasizes that contextual performance is an undeniable factor that intervenes in the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities.

4.3. Recommendation—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The Department of Education should evaluate the training essential for teachers' needs in public elementary schools and implement it effectively. Evaluating key areas and the need for training is mandatory. The execution of training and development is a necessity due to its impact on the involvement of change management in educational processes. School administrators should utilize various tools to assess the capabilities of both the teaching and non-teaching staff. Therefore, it is recommended that school administrators adopt a pay-for-performance culture within their organizations to enhance employee productivity. From my perspective, this might encourage employees to work harder and thus improve their capacity to adapt to changes and innovations. Teachers should continually engage themselves in professional development activities. Continuous professional development enhances a teacher's skill set by adding new knowledge and deepening their competency in areas where they are already productive. Realizing how to improve teacher professional development will not only improve the teacher but also the student. Lastly, researchers should conduct a mixed-methods study to understand better how contextual performance moderates the interaction between entrustment and teachers' participation in school-initiated activities.

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